

**PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE
FORMATION IN FUTURE TEACHERS**

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Abstract: This article talks about today's importance, relevance and pedagogical features of the formation of professional culture in future teachers.

Keywords: professional culture, professionalism, pedagogical activity, modernity, moral maturity, professional training.

The role of pedagogical personnel in the democratic state and civil society being established in Uzbekistan is incomparable. Because this category of staff is responsible for properly educating the young generation. In this sense, it is an urgent issue to develop the professional culture of future teachers in the process of higher pedagogical education.

In the conditions of a democratic society and a market economy, the duties of a teacher are expanding and, as a result, his professional responsibilities are increasing. In this sense, it is observed that the teacher's professional culture responds to modern needs and becomes the basis for solving problems in the educational process.

The teacher's professional culture is a practical phenomenon, which is manifested in all aspects of the teacher's activity. For this reason, special attention is being paid to the requirements for teachers in all styles. Because, in order to satisfy and respond to such demands, the professional culture of the teacher is formed. Professionalism, knowledge and modernity play an important role in the teacher's professional culture. The structure of these components can be defined as follows:

Form 1. Components of teacher's professional culture.

Accepting the professional culture of a modern teacher in such a system of components is not without reasons. Because it is the profession, knowledge, and time factors that meet the demands and needs of the teacher's work. For example, a number of requirements are set for the teacher in the educational regulatory documents, or many approaches are described in scientific research. However, all of them meet the following requirements stipulated in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education":

- ✓ Having relevant professional knowledge;
- ✓ To have professional training;
- ✓ Having moral qualities;
- ✓ Not prohibited from working in educational institutions by a court verdict.[1]

Of course, these demands have grounds. However, the main issue is to prepare teachers who will respond to them. For this reason, the structure and structure of the culture of the teaching profession is expanding. It is a product of the development of the era. When the time comes, it should be noted that the demands placed on teachers by types of education attract attention due to their specific characteristics.

It is perceived that the professional culture of the teacher of the present time has the characteristic of generality. It combines individual and general qualities. In this sense, we are of the opinion that competence, competence and assessment components are the priority in the teacher's professional culture.

Note:

Figure 2. Content of teacher's professional culture

Professional competence in teacher culture encompasses the components of maturity, mastery, and role model in one's field. This skill is theoretically formed in the process of higher education and improves in pedagogical activity. Therefore, it is appropriate to evaluate the professional maturity of the teacher according to the level of activity. We can no longer demand literal professional maturity from a young teacher, we expect a relatively high level of character maturity.

Ethical competence includes knowledge, moral virtue and democratic attitude in the professional culture of the teacher. The teacher's moral competence begins to manifest itself in the process of higher education and improves during the activity. In this place, we have the right to expect moral competence and virtue from the young teacher. The process of higher education only theoretically strengthens the teacher's moral competence. Sometimes it can perform a correctional task, but the higher education process performs an important task in the matter of professional orientation of moral competence.

Being able to evaluate one's own activity in the teacher's professional culture embodies the components of creativity, technology, competence and efficiency. A teacher's ability to control his own work or dissatisfaction with his work is an important basis for the evaluation process. Currently, evaluation of teacher's activity by external forces is widespread, which is one side of the problem. The main issue is that it is important for the teacher to be able to evaluate his own work. It is at this point that the teacher's professional maturity

and moral competence are revealed. The level of professional culture is determined as a result of the assessment. [2]

After all, we accept professional maturity, moral competence and performance evaluation as the main components of the professional culture of a modern teacher. In this case, the process of higher education performs the function of formation of professional culture, theoretical guidance and correction to a certain extent. The practical activity of the teacher ensures the manifestation of professional culture, the strengthening of skills and the emergence of experience. It is appropriate to expect professional culture from a teacher with five years or more of practical experience.

Thus, the characteristic of the modern teacher is dynamic it attracts attention. The following conclusions can be drawn in this matter:

firstly, the components of professionalism, knowledge and modernity occupy an important place in the content of the teacher's professional culture; *secondly*, in the content of the teacher's professional culture, the components of professional competence, moral competence and activity evaluation are the priority in the teacher's professional culture.

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